

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE
BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO

and

Department of Animal Science

Poultry Value Chain Training Module and Course Content

Agro-Processing, Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood
Improvement Support Project Women and Youth Empowerment
Programme.

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Content

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MODULE I :LAYER PRODUCTION

1.1 OBJECTIVES:

1. Understand the poultry value chain value
- 2, Explain the Importance of poultry production
3. Identify the different breeds of poultry
4. Make decision in poultry production

1.2 INTRODUCTION

Poultry are domesticated birds kept by humans for the eggs they produce and for meat to increase protein supply to humans. Poultry sector of agriculture had been on steady increase in terms of production and potentials all over the world. The sector had been responding to supply of desired and cost effective protein (eggs and meat) to human population.

FAO (2006) had been predicting 5 percent per annum for poultry sector growth contributing 30% share of 5 global meat supply. During the last 10-15 years improve in research had led to new methods of disease control particularly Newcastle disease, new methods of estimating energy and other nutrient requirements in poultry nutrition.

Poultry in one form or another are kept in most areas of the world and there is few social or religious taboos associated with their consumption. (Smith, 2001).

There are various types of domesticated birds that are used for production of eggs and meat. Domestic chicken constitute about 90% of total domesticated poultry population. The most important of these birds in the tropics includes:

1. Domestic fowl (*Gallus gallus*) or chicken are medium sized birds with an upright stance and characterized by fleshy red combs and wattles in the head.
2. Duck (*Anas platyrhynchos*)—medium size aquatic birds with broad bills, eyes on the side of the head fairly long neck and short legs set for back on the body and webbed feet.
3. Muscovy Duck (*Cairinamoschalata*) tenown as guard dogs because they make a lot of noise when they see people.
4. Goose (*Anseranser*) /geese-domestic geese are larger than wild with thick fowl.
5. Pea fowl (*pavo specie*) neck, an upright posture and large bodies with broad rear ends.
6. Japanese quail (*Curtonixcurtonix*) small medium size cryptically coloured bird.
7. Guinea fowl (*Numida specie*) wild birds they are timid and roost trees at night can be reared intensively for egg and meat.
8. Pigeons (*Columba livia*)

9. Ostrich (*Struthio specie*)
10. Turkey (*Meleagrisgallopova*) breeds tradition – Norplk black, mammoth Brouth and modern white turkey. Domestication of turkey's took several years which may be as a result of people hatching and rearing of young birds from eggs collected from the wild.

Poultry production had witness a rapid growth providing table eggs, meat as protein sources to the teaming populace. Employment generation through various allied enterprises such as:

- a. **Input provision** Dealership in feed ingredients such as; Maize, Groundnut cake, Soyabean meal, Palm Kernel Cake, Premixes, Probiotics, Additives, Cages, Drugs, Vaccines, Day old chicks etc.
- b. **Consultancy services** (Business plan/Feasibility in Poultry production, Veterinary Services.
- c. **Output** (Meat, Eggs, Manure, Feathers, Spent Layers, Broiler Dealers/Marketers).
- d. **Hatchery Operation** (Day Old Provision and Dealership).
- e. **Feed Mill Operations** (Production and Dealership).

Poultry production has other advantages over other Agricultural Enterprises as it has:

- Short term in terms of production investment
- Cost effective
- Efficiency in production
- Require little capital to start

Millions of people still depend on backyard or small scale poultry production, as means of livelihood. It also help the rural people to use poultry birds as a quick sources of money when the need arises. The intensive raising of birds for table egg and meat production is witnessing an upward and increasingly vibrant industry that employs millions of people in both urban, semi-urban and rural areas.

1.3 IMPORTANCE OF POULTRY PRODUCTION

- Poultry serves as a source of immediate cash income
- Provides meat and eggs as protein for household consumption
- Contributes to food security and creates employment opportunities
- Provide manure and services as organic manure for crops especially vegetables and nitrogen demanding crops like maize.
- Back yard poultry production requires small capital t start.
- Poultry birds are efficient converters of feed to meat and eggs.

- Poultry is the second most widely eaten meat in the world accounting for 30% of total meat production worldwide. Sixteen billion birds are raised annually for consumption.
- Global broiler production rose to 84.6 million tonnes in 2013.
- FAO in 2002 had placed Nigeria as the 13th largest poultry producer in the world accounting for 143 500 000 and by 2009 world production raised 50 billion from 15, 853 900,000.

1.4 PLANNING FOR POULTRY PRODUCTION AS BUSINESS

As prospective commercial farmer who intend to join the ever growing profitable and highly expanding industry there is the needs to address some fundamental questions that will make him/her to succeed.

1. What is the objective of setting the enterprise? A good objective and sound judgment will ensure that a prospective entrepreneur remains focus towards achieving the set objective.
2. What type of production system will the investor use or utilize deep litter, battery cage, wooden cage, other kinds of housing etc?
3. Do you have suitable site/farm? Is area prone to flooding, heavy winds etc?
4. It the location suitable and is supported by required infrastructure?
5. Will the production constitute environmental hazards?
6. What are the risk? What are the mitigating measures to such risks.
7. Is it Layer production or Broiler production?
8. Do the investor have the required capital?
9. Do the investor's equity sufficient or he require other sources of funds such as financial institution?
10. If funds arc to be borrowed what is the interest rate, will the interest payment consume all the anticipated Net profit?
11. Do the investor have knowledge or skills in the chosen enterprise?
12. Is there available and reliable market for products?
13. Is the new entrepreneur having a mentor in the business?
14. Where will the entrepreneur sources for input of production such as day old chicks feed/feed ingredients? A good sources of inputs such as day old chicks from reputable hatchery is one of the key fundamentals for success in the business.

Through years of interaction of with farmers it has been established that the industry is faced with myriad of problems such as:-

- Poor supervision of operations by owners, is the investor an absentee manager? Or full time manager?
- Lack of proper operational guide such as: realistic Feasibility studies with good costing in both fixed and re-current costs as well as not over ambitious revenue forecast.
- Lack of good schedules/work plan for the farm.
- Effective health programme (Vaccinations and Medication schedules)
- Lack of good, effective, genuine poultry drugs sold in the market.
- Lack of effective monitoring and regulations in the supply of veterinary drugs by governments at all levels.
- Lack of government support to the industry to protect eggs producers from unwholesome selling of candle eggs from hatcheries at cheap prices that affect domestic/local producers.
- Too many professional adviser/experts both qualified and unqualified and in some respect qualified quacks that operate in the industry without specialization, regulation or supervision that result in most investors recording heavy losses.

A prospective new entrepreneur needs to effectively equip himself/herself with all necessary relevant information in the industry before “flunging in”.

Adequate information on techniques for production ensures efficiency and profitable production.

1.5 BREEDS USED FOR COMMERCIAL POULTRY PRODUCTION

Hybrids: majority of breeds used for poultry production are hybrids birds that have been bred by large-scale international poultry breeding corporations these includes fertile eggs, day old chicks, parental breeding stocks which are imported into most tropical countries. There breeds are developed for high egg production, others for meat (broilers) and in some countries dual purpose (meat and eggs)

1.5.1 Breeds for High Egg Production

- Leghorn
- Ancona
- Minorcan

The white leghorn: is the most widely popular breed used in some countries referred to locally as “white egg producers”. Experiences had shown that people still prefer the “Brown egg”. The white leghorn breeds have the advantage of not going “broody” easily compared to other breeds on deep litter. They appear to be more heat tolerant may be this what account for the domination of this breed in the Middle East (Saudi Arabia, Egypt, etc) The birds have high feed conversion efficiency.

Rhode Island Red:- Austrolop, New Harmshire:- These are popular brown eggs producers in the tropic; Rhode Island Red especially are good egg producers and meat but possess a yellow skinned carcass which some consumers does not like, and they go broody easily.

Austrolop breed: is popular in South East Asia; they go broody easily but when cross, with white leghorn, they produce good performance.

Other breeds of birds by country location includes:-

American Breeds:

Rhode Island Red, New Hampshire, Plymouth Rock, Wyandotte, Jersey Giant

English Breeds:

Orpington, Austrolop, Light Sussex

Mediterranean Breeds:

Leghorn, Ancona

1.6:POULTRY PRODUCTION SYSTEM

According to researchers and scientist 74% world poultry meat and 68% eggs are raised in intensive system the free range and semi intensive system account for 26% and 32%.

1.6.1 FREE RANGE SYSTEM

in the rural areas and some urban communities free scavenging birds are allowed and the chickens and cockerels move on free range utilizing the available feed they can gather. They are however exposed to worms (Helminths) and have low productivity and produce 60 eggs per year. The chickens enjoy a lot of exercise, but the young chicks are pre-dispose to predators and unfavourable wealth or condition.

1.6.2 SEMI-INTENSIVE SYSTEM

this system is better than free range and inputs are introduced such as fencing some form of feeding and scavenging with improve health care and sanitation.

1.6.3 INTENSIVE

this system uses more inputs than extensive and semi-intensive system. Intensive system is market orientated production whose main objective is profit maximization. Stock numbers are high and breeds are developed through conscious breeding efforts to provide farmers with high performing birds.

1.6.4: DEEP LITTER SYSTEM

involved raising birds on a floor covered with 5-10cm of litter (locally available materials such as wood shavings, old newspaper, rice husk etc.) the litter should be dry to absorb waste and provide comfort to birds. The litter should be removed at least every 1-2 weeks. It allows for culling of unproductive birds, proper disease control and good record keeping.

1.6.5 CAGE SYSTEM

In this system the chickens are more restricted in cages and have less mobility compared to deep litter the system requires extra-investment in cages and has less labour/birds

1.7 PERFORMANCE GOALS ENTREPRENEUR SHOULD TARGET

1. Livability of birds-96%
2. Egg yield- 310eggs/bird/production cycle.
3. Feed consumption - 40kg/bird
4. Peak production - 24wks- 50wks of age of birds
5. Highest production 97% for 10 weeks

Calculating feed consumption by birds

$\frac{\text{Total feed consumed} \times 1000\text{gm}}{\text{Average number of birds} \times \text{No. of Days}} = \text{gm/bird/day.}$

Average number of birds No. of Days

MODULE II: POULTRY HOUSING

2.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Identify types of housing designs and location
2. Identify basic poultry house equipment
3. Acquire the skill of brooding chicks
4. Learn how to manage birds up to point of lay

2.2 REQUIREMENTS FOR POULTRY HOUSING

Poultry houses should not be located in areas that are prone to flooding, erosion, undulating areas unless leveled up, on water ways and areas that can blow sand dunes. Housing should be provided with enough ventilation raised and provided with necessary measures to reduce effect of heat during hot period and excessive cold during cold period. An optimum temperature of 27⁰C-30⁰C ensures birds live in a comfort zone complete blocking of east side and west side will prevent the direct effect of sun into the house in the mornings and late evenings.

Roofing materials should be products that do not easily absorb heat (such as Asbestors Aluminum) or zinc should be covered with thatch materials during heat period. Some of this measure ensures heat stress is reduced. By the nature of birds their response to increase in ambient temperature above 30⁰C is decrease in feed consumption and water consumption increases, this lead to drop in egg production and potassium toxicity when blood calcium is utilize in shell formation.

Temperatures above 32⁰C and relative humidity of 50-60% result in Alkalosis which can reduce egg shell calcification producing thin-shelled eggs in layers and leg problems in broilers. Also egg is reduced in size. Optimum temperature in broilers ensures that they are heavier at 10-19⁰C feed is also efficiently converted in optimum temperature therefore; housing holds the key to successful and profitable poultry production.

2.3 POULTRY HOUSE DESIGNS

House design for layer on deep litter

2.4: GENERAL MANAGEMENT OF POULTRY HOUSE

- Do not use egg trays from another farm
- Second hand equipment from another farm should not be used unless thoroughly disinfected.
- Avoid entry of poultry house by outsiders.
- Ensure strict vaccination programme
- Use foot baths for personal and vehicles at the gate disinfectant should be strong enough e.g Diskol © for good Biosecurity
- Burn or use deep pit to dispose dead birds.
- Remove manure, litter, dust fans and all garbage from farm
- Ensure diseased birds are isolated.
- Dead birds should be taken for post mortem immediately.
- Good quality feed should be made available to birds.
- Use birds of same age in same pen.

2.5 BROODING OF CHICKS

Brooding refers to those processes that are involved in giving comfort and managing the chick from the time they are received from the hatchery to the time they arrived the farm and managed for 8weeks.

During this period 0-8 weeks the chicks should be fed chicks mash that contains 20-22% crude protein as guide. Adequate warmth/heat is provided with good ventilation, water, antistress in the first day. Vaccinations and other medications are delivered during this period. For successful brooding the chicks are provided the much need comfort and should appear alert with bright eyes and good gait. Body temperature of chicks is about 38⁰C-39⁰C while adult bird is 40⁰C. Additional heat during brooding enables chick to attain adult body temperature.

Temperature required during brooding

1st week- 32.20C -----350C

2nd week – 290C -----320C

3rd week 260C -----290C

Broilers-----35°C

House relative humidity should be 50-70%

Before chicks arrival 2-3weeks the house should be prepared tested and be ready for the arrival of chicks. Two days to arrival floor should be covered with litter material (large wood shavings) covered with old newspaper, brooder guard should be placed two hours to the arrival of chicks feed should be provided and cool, clean water with antistress as well as additional heat should be provided. On arrival week chicks should be separated and assisted to take water.

2.5.1 Good Brooding Practices

- Chicks should not be too much under one brooder guard
- Chicks should not be frightened by dogs, cats, loud noise
- Promptly remove faeces from water

- Follow vaccination and medication schedule
- Always enter chicks house gently and carefully
- Do not rear chicks of different ages at the same times
- Give good quality feed and water
- Remove sick chick and quarantine
- Do not use chlorinate water for mixing live vaccine.

When chick arrived

- Chick for symptoms such as coughing, sneezing watery eyes, labored, breathing, diarrhea
- Provide water for few hours before feed with glucose or sugar wide especially if the ravel long distance
- For biosecurity use foot DIPs, clean shoes and limit visitors.

Light requirement during brooding of layers

- 0-3 days of chicks life -23-24hours
- 4days -1 week - 12hours
- 1-2weeks - 12hours
- 22weeks- 1 4hours
- 23-27weeks -15hours
- 27weeks - 16 hours
- Above 27weeks 16 ¹/₂ -17hours

Body Weight target during brooding

- ✓ At 6 weeks birds should be 400-480grams
- ✓ At 7 weeks birds should be 590-590grams
- ✓ At 8 weeks birds should be 590-630grams
- ✓ At 9 weeks birds should be 640-690grams
- ✓ At 10 weeks birds should be 690-750grams
- ✓ At 11 weeks birds should be 750-810grams
- ✓ At 12 weeks birds should be 810-870grams
- ✓ At 13 weeks birds should be 880-930grams
- ✓ At 14 weeks birds should be 940-990grams
- ✓ At 15 weeks birds should be 950-1050grams
- ✓ At 16 weeks birds should be above 1500grams (1¹/₂kg).

2.5.2 Signs of Healthy Chicken

- Externally clean and alert
- More freely with strong legs
- Normal voice
- Lay normal eggs
- Soft compact droppings
- Breath quietly

2.5.3 Signs of Un-Healthy Chicken

- Dull eyes and comb
- Lay less eggs
- Wet droppings (white, green, bloody)
- Unable to move
- Sneezing
- Abnormal voice
- Death

MODULE III: POULTRY FEED AND FEEDING

3.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Manage point of lay birds to end of laying period.
2. identify poultry feed and formulate feed
3. Understand heat stress management
6. Agric preneurship development including business plan in poultry production.

3.2 FEEDING REQUIREMENT OF LAYER BIRDS

All over the world various advance have made in the poultry industry to have a feed unit that supplies all the nutrient requirement of birds. However feed constitutes the major cost involved in poultry production (70-80%).

High producing birds such as broiler requires 4-5kg of feed in 7-8weeks to produce about 2kg meats.

Poultry nutritionist produce high quality feed that meets the demand of birds for various physiological functions. Layers exhibit two peak feed consumption period at the time of lay and late afternoon. Light encourages feed at cooler parts of the day or night.

During heat period high crude protein ration and increase macro minerals especially calcium ensures better egg production however more calcium added reduce palatability of feed. Oster shell or limestone chips are better utilize to increase calcium sources in feed.

Protein requirement:- for birds is the requirement for the supply of essential amino acids together with supply of suitable nitrogeneous compounds from which non-essential amino acids can be synthesized. Essential amino acids includes lysine, methionine, threonine, tryptophan, isoleucine, luecine, valine, phenylamine, histidne, arginine. Non-essential alanine, aspartic acid and glutamine.

Vitamin requirement:- vitamins are involved in enzymes systems, they are required in small quantities, actual amount depend on diet, rate growth or egg production, size of bird and possibly climate. Imbalance of vitamins can lead to serious disorders. Housed poultry are entirely dependent on vitamins present in compounded feed therefore it is essential to provide vitamins in correct amount.

Vitamin A:- if vitamin A in diet is too low, growth rate is reduced and mortality increases, egg production is reduced.

Vitamin D is synthesized by skin of chickens when exposed to sunlight. In intensive system there is need for supplementation if deficient birds will be unable to use calcium and phosphorous in diet. Vitamin D and calcium, phosphorous in diet are essential otherwise egg shell formation is affected. Lack of vitamin D causes reduction in chicks and oestoporosis in adult.

Vitamin K:- essential for blood clotting, if deficient hemorrhages can occur in legs, breast and wings and delayed clotting time.

Vitamin E:- Unstable and easily destroyed by oxidising agents especially rancid oil deficiency affect nervous system called encephalomalacia or “crazy chick disease,”

Vitamin B complex:- thiamin (vitamin B₁) riboflavin (B₂) pyridoxin (B₆), pantothenic acid, nicotinic acid, choline, B₁₂, biotin and folic acid. Vitamin B₂ deficiency lead to curly toe paralysis in chicks, Nicotine essential in feathering, choline in fat metabolism, B₁₂ for development of red blood cells.

Minerals:- calcium and phosphorous interact with each other both before and after absorption from digestive tract. Excessive amount of either or low amount interfere with the utilization of the other, requirements of this minerals are influenced by vitamin D in the diet. Requirement of calcium and phosphorous increases as level vitamin D decreases and vice-versa.

Carbohydrate:- is the energy source for daily activities which is vital in the life of the children.

3.2.1 Nutrient Content of Poultry feeds

3.2.2 Poultry Feed Processing:

Various feed when processed has the following advantage

- ❖ Increasing digestibility of the feed
- ❖ Increase palatability of the feed
- ❖ Increase intake by the birds
- ❖ Reduce feed wastage
- ❖ Enhance storage and preservation
- ❖ Make handling easier
- ❖ Reduce deleterious effect of the feed

Various types of processing include

Grinding, pelleting, waffering, heating, cooking, roasting, smoking, drying, freezing e.t.c.

3.2.3 Feed ingredients and Composition

Cereals	Crude protein
Maize	9%
Wheat	12%
Sorghum	10%
Millet	11%
Rice	7%
Fish meal	68-70%
Groundnut cake	40%
Soyabean meal	44%
Palm kernel cake	20%
Meat meal	48%
Blood meal	80%

Cereals also contain:

10-15% other carbohydrates

2-5% crude fat

2-5% Ash

12-17% Moisture

3.2.4 Feed requirement for 1000 pullet (day old to End of Laying period)

Age of bird	Feed required
Day old to 4weeks	Chicks mash 600k /25kg/bag=24bags
4 -8weeks	Chicks mash 125kg/25kg/bag=50bags
4-8weeks	Grower mash 1750kg/ 25kbag=70bags
12-16weeks	Grower mash 2450kg/ 25kg=98kg
16-20weeks	Grower mash 280kg/ 25kg/bag=112bag
20-24 weeks	

Summary of feed 0-24 weeks

From week 24 or when feed consumption/day reaches 5bags/1000birds

3.2.5 Feed Requirement For 1000 Broilers

Age of birds	Quantity of feed required
Day old to 2weeks	Broiler starter 300kg/ 25kg/bag =12bags
2-4weeks	Broiler starter 750kg/25kg/bags =30bags
4-6weeks	Broiler finisher 1250kg/25kg/bag= 50bags
6-8weeks	Broiler finisher 1600kg/25kg/bag 64bags

Feed Menu Chickens

Cold Season

S/N	Feed ingredient	Chicks mash kg	Grower mash kg	Layer mash kg	Broiler starter kg
1.	Fish meal	15	-	18	15
2.	G/nut cake	150	150	200	250
3.	Soy bean meal	50	-	100	50
4.	Palm kernel cake	0	50	25	-
5.	Maize	550	400	400	590
6.	Wheat bran	150	350	200	50
7.	Lysine	1 ^½	^½	1 ^½	1 ^½
8.	Methionine	^½	1 ^½	^½	^½
9.	Limestone	15	30	20	20
10.	Salt	2 ^½	2 ^½	2 ^½	2 ^½
11.	Bone meal	13	13	18	18
12.	Premix	2 ^½	2 ^½	2 ^½	2 ^½
	Total	1000kg	100kg	1000kg	1000kg

During the hot season reduce energy sources increase protein sources and calcium sources.

3.3 EFFECTIVE TACKLING OF HEAT STRESS DURING HOT PERIODS

Housing: Design and location should be environmentally friendly, should have good ventilation, good orientation, have enough tree shade roofs should not encourage extensive absorption of solar radiation, well insulated, house are better use of fans to cool the house is also practiced.

- Providing high air speed which helps reduce heat stress by removing hot air.
- Internal recirculation fans can also be used.
- Use of evaporative cooling system in house as water evaporates, energy is required from the air and heat is lost resulting in cooler air.
- Water can be evaporated using cooling pads or from atomized nozzles.

Evaporative cooling system

- Help birds maintain heat balance.
- Reduce panting frequency.

- Help maintain feed consumption.

House Temperature and Stocking Density

When poultry house temperature is at various level stocking density (i.e. space/bird) requirement varies:

Mean House Temperature Liter/Space/Bird	Space/1.5kg Bird on Deep
20°C	01.54
25°C	0.67
30°C	0.90
35°C	1.35

Water consumption/1000 birds (broilers)

Age of Birds	Temperature of water	
	at 20°C	at 30°C
1 st week of bird	24liters	50liters
3 rd week of bird	100liters	210 liters
6 th week of bird	280liters	600liters

Lack of water can retard the growth and impair eggs production in layers.

Estimate of water intake by layers 100 layers

Age of Bird	Water Intake Liters/Day
0-2weeks	4-5
2-5 weeks	7-10
5-10 weeks	15
10-20 weeks	18
Adult layers	20-30

The body of birds contains about 60% water and eggs have about 65% water. Water aids in the distribution of nutrients and removal of toxic materials. Water help in control of body temperature especially in hot weather condition. Panting by birds is an essential heat loss mechanism and lack of water lead to death by hyperthermia; therefore birds consume more water at high ambient temperature.

MODULE IV: POULTRY DISEASES AND MANAGEMENT

4.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Identify and manage poultry diseases
2. Identify layer birds vaccination schedules
3. Identify layer birds vaccines

4.2 HEALTH OF LAYER BIRDS

Birds that are well fed and managed from handling at day old to the farm, vaccinated against known diseases that are economic in an area remain healthy.

If there is disease outbreak the prompt attention of professional is required (veterinary doctor, nutritionist) are highly required.

Sick birds should be promptly removed and isolated, strict sanitary measures should be employed.

4.3 POULTRY DISEASES

4.3.1 Bacterial Diseases of Poultry

A. bacterial diseases

cause(s)

Infectious coryza (Roup)	
Chronic Respiratory Disease (CRD)	<i>Haemophilus agallinarum</i>
Avian Respiratory Mycoplasmosis	<i>Mycoplasma gallisepticum</i>
Infectious synovitis	<i>Mycoplasma synovial</i>
Fowl cholera	<i>Pasteurella multocida</i>
Avian pseudotuberculosis	<i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>
Fowl typhoid (salmonellosis)	<i>Salmonella Pullorum</i>
Pullorum diseases in chicks	<i>Salmonella gallinarum</i>
Fowl typhoid in adult	<i>Salmonella pullorum</i>
Escherichia coli infections	<i>Salmonella gallinarum</i>
- Collesptecernia	} In chicks
- Air sacculitis	
Ulcerative enteritis	(Quail disease)
Necrotic enteritis	<i>Clostridia perfringes</i>
Butulism	<i>Clostridium butulinum</i>
Avian tuberculosis	<i>Mycobacterium avium</i>

4.3.2 Viral Diseases of Poultry

1. New Castle Disease (ND)
2. Avian influenza (fowl plague) “Avian flu”
3. Mareks disease
4. Infectious bursal disease (Gumboro)
5. Infections bronchitis
6. Infectious laryngotracheitis (ILT)
7. Avian pox
8. Avian infectious anemia

4.3.3 Fungal Diseases of Poultry

1. Aspergillosis (Brooder Pneumonia)
2. Mycotoxicosis
3. Aflatoxicosis

4.3.4 Parasitic Diseses of Poultry

Ectoparasite (vector)

Parasitic Diseases

Round worm: Ascaridiagalli	Ticks
Nematodes- Nematodes infection	Mites
Trematodes- infections	Lice
Cestodes (Tapeworms) infection	

Protozoan Diseases of Poultry

Causes

- | | |
|-------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. Coccidiosis | <i>Eimeriaspp</i> |
| 2. Histomoniasis | <i>Histomonasmelegridis</i> |
| 3. Trichomoniasis | <i>Trichomonasgallinae</i> |
| 4. Hexamiatisasis | <i>Hexamonasmeliagridis</i> |

4.3.5 Nutritional Diseases

Protein: deficiency in essential amino acids can cause- feather pecking” cannibalism, ruffled feathers, perosis or slipping of gastronemius tendon retardation of growth, fatty liver syndrome.

Fats: Essential fatty acids- deficiency causes - retardation in growth, lack of proper function of liver, lack of absorption of fat soluble vitamins (A’ and E lead to lack of resistance to respiratory infection.

Vitamins: A deficiency – causes weakness, imbalance, retardation in body growth, ruffled feathers, abnormally large comb/testes, chicks prone to conjunctivitis, CRD, coccidiosis.

Hypovitaminosis Deficiency young/growing in chicks, causes stunted growth nutrients large layers paralysis.

Vitamin E - deficiency mortality of embryo at 4days of incubation.

Hypovitaminosis K- Green vegetables as sources blood clotting factor, blood tinged feathers/ mortality upto50% haemorrhages in breast muscles.

Vitamin C deficiency not well defined

- In heat stress very good incorporate therefore incorporate 20mg/lb of feed
- Helps in reducing diseases infections
- Resistance to E coli infection

Vitamin Bi found in Grains and husks required more in layers and play a role in Nerve functioning deficiency leads to “star gazing”.

Vitamin B2 (Riboflavin) essential for normal metabolism deficiency affect nerve, body growth, causing “curly toes”, drop in wings and head than diarrhea develop after 10 days, slight decline in eggs production.

Mineral Deficiency

- Calcium and Phosphorous deficiency –results in rickets, reduces egg shell quality
- Sodium deficiency lead to less growth, sudden drop in egg production, tendency for cannibalism, diarrhea.

4.3.6 Miscellaneous Diseases of Poultry

- Heat stroke
- Proventriculosis peritonitis
- Impaction of crop
- Prolapse of cloaca - increase, which is due to peristalsis in layers, or – fusa - riotoxins, or homoeopathic drug, podophyllum in drinking water.
- Cloacitis- pasty exudates with fowlodour
- Smoothening -inadequate breathing
- Carbon monoxide poisoning
- Egg bound conditions
- Impaction of oviduct
- Thin shelled/deformed eggs
- Avian hysteria- excitement, fear
- Caged layer fatigue- Leg weakness

Metabolic

- Toxic fat syndrome
- Leg weakness in broilers
- Fatty liver syndrome

Thin shelled eggs

May be due to: calcium deficiency, vitamin D. Deficiency, obesity of hen, egg drop syndrome, viral infection.

Swollen head syndrome- 4-6 weeks are affected or broilers, 24-30 weeks broiler breeders cause unknown.

Metabolic Diseases

1. Toxic fat syndrome- excess fluid in abdominal cavity, pericardium in subcutaneous tissue as jelly like fluid cause by toxin in feed.
2. Leg weakness in broiler
3. Fatty liver syndrome- deposition of fat in the liver.

Caused by excessive intake of energy and unrestricted feeding in layers, or low calcium, or stress, or vitamins, and micro nutrients deficiency, or high Temperature, toxins, deficiency of amino acids.

Infectious *Coryza*

Lyragotry chaeties infection

Other infectious diseases symptoms

4.3.7 Important Diseases of Poultry causes symptoms, treatment and prevention

Disease	Causative organism	Symptoms	Treatment	Prevention
Bacterial				
1. Bacillary white diarrhea or (pollorum disease)	Salmonella Pullurom	Whitish diarrhea, refusal to eat huddling wings hanging down yens chicks die without showing signs, blindness, lameness may occur.	Euroflaxacine furazolidone, sulphadiazine for 5-10days in feed or water, this can cause egg drop in laying birds use additional lactose for chicks	Transrnitted through eggs good sanitation in farm required
2. Fowl typhoid	Salmonella gallinarum	Loss of appetite yellowish, on vent watery, greenish diarrhea, otherwise whitish. Affect bird of any age	Sulphadiazine furazolidone, euroflaxacin sulphaquinoxacin sulphathazole sulphonarnides sulphathazole. Sulphurdrugs cause egg drop in layers	As above lactose indiet chicks which lower PH of intestines and increase concentration volatile fatty acids of VFA that has good antibacterial activity

3. Fowl cholera	<p>Pasteurella mutocida\ E-coli which infection in broilers show similar symptoms.</p> <p>Treatment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Furazolidone - Neomycin- Doxycillin - Ampicillin 	<p>Loss of appetite labored breathing, dark droppings. high temperature, reduces that turn almost black, loss of appetite, diarrhea, bluish comb diarrhea becoming yellowish greenish</p>		Good sanitation
4. Infection coryza	Haemophilusparagallinarum	<p>Young and adult birds are affected. Chronically infected carrier bird can introduce the disease. Foul smelling discharge from nostrils or eyes wattles swollen, sneezing I oyspnea low mortality</p>	<p>Trimethoprim sulphate drugs entloxacin ethnomycin gentamycin</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include water sanitizers\ - Sanitation on Low density avoid over crowding
5. CRD Avian respiratory disease)	Mycoplasma gallisepticum	<p>4- 10 weeks birds are affected, broilers occasionally old birds cause sneezing and coughing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oxytetracycline - Terramycin - Streptomycin - Erythrumycin 	Good management

4.4: GOOD AND GENUINE POULTRY DRUGS FOR SUCCESSFUL MANAGEMENT

4.5 PROBLEM OF EGG DROP IN LAYER BIRD PRODUCTION

Egg production drops may be as a result of several factors

1. Problem of disease such as viral, bacterial or protozoan (new castle, fowl typhoid, fowl cholera, coccidiosis etc).
2. Problems of the environment (house temperature too high or too low). Poor ventilation leading to excessive ammonia build up, improper lightening, sudden change in house temperature, loud noise by birds, vehicles, visitors, birds, dogs etc.
3. Problems of inadequate nutrition through improper balanced nutrients (protein, energy, minerals, vitamins fat and oil and water). Inadequate energy levels (from feed energy sources maize wheat offal etc)

Sden changing of feed ingredients or feed texture which may cause transient drop in feed intake leading to drop in egg production.

4. Infection by external parasites such as lice which lead to anemia and drops in egg production.
5. Some drugs usage, serious abuse in the use of anti biotics in poultry production can cause egg production drop especially when not properly handled.

4.6 RECORD KEEPING IN LAYER BIRD PRODUCTION

Various important records that need to be kept are as follows:

1. Input record – feed, medication
2. Expenditure record - purchases, sales
3. Output record, eggs production, manure, empty bags
4. Health record

4.6.1 Vaccination/medication schedule

1. 1st day of chick life- mareks NDV 1/0- done in the hatcheryif not sure repeat after 3-7 days of chicks arrived.
2. 1st day - 5 days- Antistress
3. Day 10- gumboro 1st dose
4. Day 24 gumboro 2nd dose
5. Week 3 (for five days) - coccidiostat
6. Week 4- NDV (Lasota)
7. Week 6 (for five days) coccidiostat
8. Week 7 NDV komoro 1st dose fowl pox vaccine
9. Week 8 (1 day) Dewormer
10. 10.Wcek 9 (for 5days)- coccidiostat)
11. Week 12 (for 5days) cocidiostat
12. Week 13 Dbeaking
13. Week 16- NDV komorov 2nd Dose

MODULE V: BROILER PRODUCTION

5.1. OBJECTIVES

1. Understand the purpose of broiler bird production
2. Identify the feed and feeding for broiler birds
3. Identify and formulate feeding for broiler birds
4. Manage housing and diseases of broiler birds

5.2 INTRODUCTION

Broilers are meat type chicken that are tender and grow fast attaining a market weight from 6 – 8 weeks. Weighing 1.5 – 2.2kg. The broiler meat industry is one of the fastest growing segments of the poultry production value chain. The increase acceptance of broiler meat in the diet of Nigerians had further made the production of broilers in cities and rural areas a means of livelihood for teeming farmers. Poultry production in general had taken a quantum leap over the years. In order to get maximum benefit in the broiler production enterprise a prospective investor/farmer needs to have sound technical knowledge on breeds, housing, feeding, management disease management in order to succeed. The pertinent question that needs to be asked before embarking are:

1. What quantity will I produce?
2. Who will buy?
3. What feed to be used?
4. How do I add value?

5.3 TYPES OF BROILER BIRD BREEDS

The common broiler breeds are the white colour types while others are Hybro, vencobb, bobcobb etc.

5.4: HOUSING AND MANAGEMENT OF BROILER BIRDS

A comfortable and good broiler house holds one of the key to successful production and is essential in achieving good growth and body weight gain in broiler farming therefore good site should be selected where:

1. There is sufficient area
2. Reparably high land not water logged area
3. Area with good water supply
4. Easy transportation
5. Source of electricity
6. Market access for both inputs procurement and output sales.

House should be designed with good ventilation and fully covered east-west to prevent direct sunlight into house, space requirement for birds is at least 1sqft/bird, rectangular.

5.4.1 Management of Broiler Birds

1. Good breed and fast-growing day-old chicks should be purchased from reputable dealers and hatcheries.
2. Before chicks arrival the house should be warm and tested:
 - Disinfect room and apply litter and disinfect litter material
 - Clean feeders, drinkers and spray brooder guards
 - Ensure temperature in house is between 37⁰C – 39⁰C.
 - Prepare house 24 hours before chick's arrival
 - Continuous light
 - Litter material should be wood shavings
3. Feeding

Recent research and advances in broiler feeding indicates high feed conversion efficiency due to genetic improvement of the birds. Broilers on voluntary feed intake is linked to growth therefore ensure good quality feed with the required nutrients for faster growth.

If birds are not growing as desired not only feed intake may be the problem but other factors ie deficiency of essential nutrients but also energy, temperature, stocking density, feeder and water space. Good water supply to broilers lead to better feed intake, under

moderate environmental condition the water consume by broilers is approximately twice that of feed consume ie two grain of water per due grain of feed. Most important factor influencing feed conversion in broiler and other birds is ambient temperature of poultry house. Broiler performs best when there is minimum variation in house temperature over a 24 hour period. During cooler periods broilers eat more feed but the feed intake that is converted to warm the body do not add up to growth. During high temperatures they eat less and convert the feed less efficiently.

Feed wastage arise when plenty of feed is supplied especially during brooding therefore small quantities are always advised otherwise increase feed wastage leads to lower profitability health of birds also influences feed conversion, with sick broilers not performing well watch for early signs of disease.

As feed is the major cost in poultry production which significantly affect production, improper feed not only affects performance but is a precursor to diseases.

5.4.2 Target Weight Gain for Broiler Birds

Age in days	Weight in gms/day
1 st day	Chicks should be about 20gm/bird
2 nd day	22gm
3 rd day	24gm
4 th day	26gm
21 st day	58gm
4 weeks – 5 weeks	1kg and above
6 weeks	1.5kg and above
8 weeks	2kg and above

5.4.3 Prevention of Diseases

- Use good day old chicks
- Disinfect house
- Avoid visitors
- Keep feed free from contamination
- Give good water clean and fresh always
- Follow medication and vaccination schedule
- Foot bath should be provided
- Dispose off dead birds

5.5 COST ESTIMATES FOR 1000 BROILER PRODUCTION CYCLE AS AT JULY 2019

5.5.1 Fixed Cost

1.	Contribution from land	-	N40,000.00/annum
2.	Contribution from infrastructure	-	N60,000.00/annum
	Total	=	N25,000.00/cycle of production

3.	Equipment	Qty	Unit Price	Total
i.	Chicks tray	20	150	N3000
ii.	Chicks feeder	20	20	N3000
iii.	Adult feeder	25	25	N11,250
iv.	Adult drinker	25	25	N11,250.

@ 10% depreciation = contribution/cycle = 1000/cycle

Summary of fixed cost of production/cycle = N54,500.00

5.5.2 Operation Cost

1. Cost of Day old broiler chick $1100 \times 200 = \text{N}220,000.00$
2. Feed
 - i. Broiler starter 0 – 5 weeks @ 1.3kg/bird
 $= 52 \text{ bags} \times 3500 = \text{N}182,000.00$
 - ii. Broiler finisher 5 – 9 weeks @ 4kg/bird
 $= 160 \text{ bags} \times 3450 = \text{N}552,000.00$
3. Medication/Vaccination cost = N4000.00
4. Wages @ N10,000.00/head x 2 months = N30,000.00

Total = N
 + 10% consultancy and other
 Miscellaneous expenditure = N50,000
 = N1,119, 000.00

5.5.3 Summary of Production Cost

Fixed Cost Contribution + Operating Cost

N54,500 + N1,119,000 = N1,623,508.00

@N1623.50 as per bird cost of production

5.5.4 Revenue Forecast

1050 (2kg – 2.5kg birds)

Price/weight = 950

= 2kg x 1050 = N950/kg = 2100kg x N950

Gross revenue = N1,995,000.00

Less expenditure = N371,492/cycle

Add cost of manure = N60,000

= N431,492.00

Live Weight Sales

1050 birds x N1300 = N1,365,000.00

This is why producers of broiler selling @ live weight always run at lost or barely break even while processing and selling at dead weight attract better price.

5.6 BROILER VACCINATION/MEDICATION SCHEDULE

1. On chicks arrival
 Glucose in water then
2. Neimelh (Terramycine Chicks formula) or Neocryl in water
3. 7th Day – Gumboro I vaccine in water
 10th Day – Losota I vaccine in water
 Follow each vaccine with multivitamin
 Amino grow® Liquid in water
4. 21st Day Gumboro II

24th Day Lasota II

5. 4 weeks of life = pipeparazine in water 1 day only
6. The Diclosol liquid in water for 5 days or Embazin® for 5 days

Note adjust Deworming and Coccidiostat on demand or if the needs arises.

INPUT PRICES AS @ JULY 2019

1. Day Old chicks = N200/chick
2. Feed broiler starter = N3,500
Broiler finisher = N3,450

OUTPUT PRICE AS @ JULY 2019

- 2kg live weight = N1200 – N1300
Dead weight = N900 – N950/kg